

Surface geochemical and mineralogical methods for the environmentally friendly exploration in the glaciated terrains

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Advanced surface geochemical sampling and analysis techniques offer a cost-effective and environmentally friendly set of ore prospecting methods for glaciated areas. Traditionally in the glaciated areas, conventional methods based on the secondary transport of the glacier have been used to determine the origin of surface boulders, heavy minerals and till geochemistry. Due to the variable glacial history, the directions of glaciers' movement, and the complex stratigraphy, tracing the origin can be difficult. Instead, surface geochemical techniques based on the elements' composition of different sample media such as upper sediments and organic soils, plants and even snow provide a direct signal of underlying surface sediment-covered or blind mineralization.

Techniques which are based on the migration of mobile metal ions from mineralization in the bedrock through the top of the bedrock and the sedimentary cover to the upper part of the soil can be used in exploration for all types of elements and their associations. Great benefit is that practically all types of materials, i.e., mineral and organic sediments, plants and even snow are suitable sample media. Easy sampling and sample processing procedure with relatively low analytical costs make these techniques effective in mineral exploration.

Different sample materials and geochemical analysis methods have been studied recently for mineral exploration in vulnerable northern areas. Good examples are the EU-funded projects 'New exploration technologies' (NEXT) and 'Sustainable exploration for orthomagmatic (critical) raw materials in the EU: Charting the road to the green energy transition' (SEMACRET), where the target areas have been in southern and eastern Finnish Lapland. The mobile metal ion based geochemical signal is seen in upper soil horizons (mineralized and organic), in different parts of plants, and in snow. Migrated metal ions accumulate first to the upper soil onto the surface of mineral grains and organic materials forming the exogenic geochemical signal. The so called trap sites can be variable, such as the surface of mineral grains, clay minerals, different hydroxides, and organic compounds. Weakly bounded ions are possible to dissolve with weak or selective leaches. There are plenty of commercial leaching methods available for extracting metal ions from certain mineral traps. The same layer, i.e., upper soil is also a main source for nutrients which plants are collecting using roots forming the basis for biochemistry. In the areas of shallow transported cover roots also can uptake nutrients directly from the bedrock. Plants use major and trace elements as construction materials for trunk, branches, and leaves/needles.

One of the latest advances in sample media is snow. During wintertime, the same mobile ions continue moving upward from the upper soil with water vapour, carbon dioxide and hydrocarbons to accumulate and trap into snow crystals. The bottom part of the snow cover gives the most stable sampling media because of the longest deposition history and the coverage of the upper snow layers which act as a shelter from atmospheric contamination. In addition, the lowest layer is in contact with the ground and is influenced by the gases and heat coming from the underlying soil and bedrock. Snow covers the landscape several months each year in large areas in the Northern Hemisphere. Snowing periods and the snow properties are constant in a regional scale, which gives a good foundation for large and comparable geochemical exploration.

In addition to the leaching-based geochemistry, there are huge amounts of new portable geochemical as well as mineralogical analysers available to support exploration work. Development of those analysers, such as pXRF, pLIBS, pXRD, hyperspectral analysers, and pRAMAN have been intense during last 10-15 years. Benefit of portable analysers is direct analysis in the field, which provides the quick and reliable analysis of the large group of elements and minerals without significant sample pre-processing. This diminishes need for the laboratory analyses which lower the analytical costs and provides real-time directing of sampling and research. This is supported by the on-site indicator mineral concentration techniques. The development of these techniques as a part of surficial geochemical exploration was done, for example, in the ERDF-funded on-site analytical development projects of the indicator mineral research for the critical metals and minerals, and Au (Indika and Indika Au projects). However, advanced laboratory analysis techniques are needed to confirm the analytical results. For example, field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) and mineral liberation analysers (MLA) support the automated identification of indicator minerals. In addition, high-resolution and laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometers (HR-ICP-MS and LA-ICP-MS) provide trace element and isotope analyses. Those techniques are largely used nowadays and are required, for example, in the recent development work related to sulfidic mineral fingerprinting as a part of indicator mineral research, the development which is done in the EIT Raw Material funded project 'Enhanced use of heavy mineral chemistry in exploration targeting' (MinExTarget).